

ANAYSIS OF THE COMPOSITE STRUCTURE OF TILTING TRAIN EXPRESS (TTX)

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SUMMARY: In this paper, finite element analysis was conducted to design sandwich structures of composite carbody of a Korean train, Tilting Train eXpress(TTX). At first, we determined the lower bound of the carbody thickness through the analysis of its unit model. On the basis of the lower bound, various load cases, such as static vertical, compressive and torsional load according to JIS E 7105 were analyzed by finite element analysis and the structural safety of the composite carbody structure was inspected to determine the thickness of the composite sandwich structure. The result showed that all the considered cases satisfied the design limit. The weight of the composite carbody is about 40 % less than that of aluminum one.

A train prototype was manufactured for static loading tests to determine structural strength and verify the safety of railway rolling stock. Before we execute the loading test, the strain sensor locations were decided from the result of structural loading analysis. 130 points of sensor location could be determined. The static loading test was simulated by FE analysis to estimate strain on the sensor location, to compared with the loading test results. Using the same FE model with static loading test, modal analysis was performed to estimate the natural frequency of train prototype,

KEYWORDS: composite carbody of train, composite joint structure, finite element analysis, Tilting Train eXpress(TTX)

INTRODUCTION

The tilting trains offer an efficient solution to attain higher speed as they can be operated on the existing track, due to their tilting mechanism on curved track. The weight reduction of carbody structures is of great concern in developing high speed tilting train for the normal operation of the tilting system and the reduction of the cost of railway repair and maintenance [1]. The use of composite materials for the carbody structures has many advantages due to their excellent material properties, such as high specific strength and stiffness, long-life durability, and the possibility of lightweight product. In developed countries, composite materials have been used for driver's cabs, interior/exterior equipments for railway train, and they are now developing the train carbody structure with the composite materials applied. In this paper, finite element analysis was conducted to analyze and design the composite structure of Tilting Train eXpress(TTX) with a service speed of 180km/h. The carbody of TTX is composed of composite sandwich structure, the skin and core of which are Graphite/Epoxy fabric and aluminium-honeycomb, respectively. To determine the thickness

of composite carbody structure, static load tests were performed and the structural safety of the composite carbody structure designed through recursive finite element analysis was verified by these tests of the train prototype. In addition, structural analysis was conducted to suggest a design of the joint part of composite carbody and metal under-frame. The train prototype was manufactured for static loading tests according to JIS E 7105 [2], and the static loading test was simulated by FE analysis to estimate strain levels on the sensor locations, and to compare with the loading test results.

CARBODY STRUCTURE ANALYSIS & DESIGN

In order to design sandwich structures of composite carbody, finite element analysis (FEA) was performed according to the procedure as follows. At first, we determined the lower bound of the carbody thickness through the analysis of its unit model [3]. As an analysis result, the stress level of the unit model with the minimum design limit thickness of 2 mm skin, and 20 mm core, was very low.

On the basis of the result of lower bound, various static load tests, such as static vertical, compressive and torsional load tests according to JIS E 7105 were simulated by finite element analysis. The structural safety of the composite carbody structure was inspected to determine the thickness of the composite sandwich structure. A detailed train model without reinforcing metal frame was constructed to estimate structural safety of composite structure of carbody.

A composite carbody is the sandwich structure, composed of Gr/Ep skin and aluminium honeycomb core. The under-frame parts, such as bolster, cross-frame, and center-sill, are made by metallic material, and their mechanical properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Material properties of composites and metals

	Under-frame (SUS, Steel)			
	SMA490B	SUS301L-LT	SS400	SPA-H
Modulus, E(GPa)	210	183	200	200
Strength, S(MPa)	370	220	250	250
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Density, ρ (kg/m ³)	7900	7900	7900	7900

	Composite – sandwich structure	
	Skin (Gr/Ep Fabric)	Core (Al Honeycomb)
E_1 (GPa)	55.5	0.17
E_2 (GPa)	48.3	0.17
E_{12} (GPa)	3.81	1480
S_1 (MPa)	642.2	150
S_2 (MPa)	548.9	250
S_{12} (MPa)	123.4	170
ν_{12}	0.099	0.996
ρ (kg/m ³)	1600	55

The mechanical property test of the Gr/Ep fabric was executed to have the properties of composite skin [4]. However, since some material properties of honeycomb core, such as the longitudinal and transverse directional stiffness, were not obtained from the manufacturer, these properties were calculated using a theory, based on the geometric shape of honeycomb core [5]. Other metal and non-metal properties are used from reference 6 and 7.

The FE model and the load & boundary conditions of each loading case are shown in Fig. 1. The model using 2D shell elements (S4R) and 1D beam elements (B31) has 16,919 nodes and 16,402 elements. A commercial code MSC/PATRAN was utilized as a pre&post-processor, and ABAQUS as a solver.

To obtain an optimal thickness of composite carbody, FE analysis was conducted iteratively, while varying the thickness of sandwich skin and core. The results are summarized in Table 2, and it showed that all the considered cases recorded low level of stress and Tsai-Wu index. The case 2 and case 3 satisfied the design limit that deflection at the under-frame under the vertical loading condition should be less than 15.9mm, except case 1. The total weight of the specified thickness was less than 4.88ton, which results in more than 40% weight reduction for aluminium carbody train.

Fig. 1: The FE model and the load & boundary condition

Table 2: The summary of the analysis results [4-7]

		$t_{skin}(mm)$	$t_{core}(mm)$	Max. stress (MPa)	Max def. (mm)
Vertical load	case 1	2	20	54.6	16.7
	case 2	2	30	53.5	15.1
	case 3	2.5	20	45.2	14.4
Compressive load	case 1	2	20	101.0	-
	case 2	2	30	89.9	-
	case 3	2.5	20	64.7	-
Tortional load	case 1	2	20	25.1	-
	case 2	2	30	26.4	-
	case 3	2.5	20	22.8	-

From the above result, structural analysis was performed with the modified model to which carbody shape was changed, and the metal frame reinforcements were introduced in the composite carbody structure. The metal frames were inserted near window and door on which stress concentrated, and the connecting parts of carbody, roof, pantograph, etc. 2D shell elements and 1D beam elements had been utilized for metal under-frame and composite sandwich structure, and for reinforcing frames of the FE model, respectively. There were 29,851 nodes and 32,589 elements in this analysis model.

The beam element properties were the sectional area and moment of inertia, calculated from the sectional shape of reinforcing frames.

The FE model of carbody and reinforcing frames are shown in Fig. 2. Figure 3 shows the structural analysis results.

As shown in Fig. 3, maximum stress of the composite structure was 59.4 MPa, occurring between the window frames and the joint part. However, it was much less than the fiber directional strength of composite material, 642.2 MPa. In addition, the maximum deflection at the under-frame was 14.8mm, which was less than the design limit.

Fig. 2: The FE model of carbody and reinforcing frames

Fig. 3: (a) Fiber dir. stress in composite skin at compressive loading (MPa),
(b) deflection of under-frame at vertical loading (y-dir., mm)

JOINT PART ANALYSIS & DESIGN

In development of a composite carbody tilting train, the structural safety is especially emphasized on the joint parts between composite carbody and metal under-frame, because it is directly related to the safety of passengers. It is well known that mechanical fastening and adhesive bonding are the two typical joining method to splice two different materials like composite and metals. In joint parts, serious stress concentration could occur near a hole of mechanical fastening, and it may be serious cause of failure in joint part. Thus, it is strongly needed to select a proper design in joint parts and to optimise detail shapes and dimensions.

A detail structural analysis of initial joint part designs was performed under bending and compression loading conditions, and structural safety of each design case was compared. For the three kinds of initial designs, different finite element models were constructed with 3D

solid elements (C3D8). The FE models and the information of node and elements are represented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: 3 types of initial design and FE model shape

In the FE model, it is supposed that composite skin, honeycomb core, and metal stiffener are perfectly bonded. It is assumed three load types, which are inward bending load (2.3 kN), outward bending load (2.3 kN), and compressive load (0.58 kN). In each case, the magnitude of load was calculated on the based of centrifugal force and weight of carbody, air-conditioner, and pantograph. Regarding an extreme loading situation in FE analysis, adhesive bonding was not reflected in joint part modelling. Thus, the constraint of rivet was only considered as boundary condition.

Maximum deflection and stress distribution in the composite skin and metal stiffener were obtained and compared each other in Table 3. As a result, it was found that the type 3 was the most outstanding design of all. Comparing with the results of type 1 and type 3, it is known that the design of metal stiffener with honeycomb inside is much more effective than the design with empty inside, to relax stress concentration on joint part.

Table 3: FE analysis results of initial designs

Load type	Stress & deformation	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3
Inward bending	Composite skin (MPa)	410	1430	303
	Metal stiffener (MPa)	702	758	302
	Max. deformation (mm)	3.5	44	3.26
Outward bending	Composite skin (MPa)	406	1430	302
	Metal stiffener (MPa)	707	753	361
	Max. deformation (mm)	3.5	44	3.26
Compressive	Composite skin (MPa)	3.45	9.8	1.6
	Metal stiffener (MPa)	10.5	10.6	5.65
	Max. deformation (mm)	0.028	0.71	0.029

Based on the results of initial design models, two types of new design with modified shape of metal stiffener were suggested (Fig. 5). And the same analysis procedure as above was followed. Inward and outward bending loads were applied in structural analysis, but compressive load, was excluded because of low stress level.

The analysis results are summarized in Table 4. The type 4 shows lower stress level, as well as enhanced stress relaxation than those of type 5, on the whole load cases. Consequently, we could be aware of the excellence of the modified design and suggested that the type 4 is the most suitable design for the joint part.

Fig. 5: (a) The shape of modified design, (b) fiber dir. stress of composite skin on inward bending load(MPa, Type 4)

Table 4: FE analysis results of modified designs

Load type	Stress & deformation	Type 4	Type 5
Inward bending	Composite skin (MPa)	202	279
	Metal stiffener (MPa)	216	461
	Max. deformation (mm)	2.20	2.39
Outward bending	Composite skin (MPa)	201	273
	Metal stiffener (MPa)	216	448
	Max. deformation (mm)	2.20	2.36

STATIC LOADING TEST

Fig. 6: Photograph of train prototype

A train prototype was manufactured for static loading test to determine structural strength and verify the safety of railway rolling stock. Gr/Ep fabric composite was applied to the prototype carbody. This prototype was manufactured by Hankuk Fiber Co., which was cured as a single piece in a huge autoclave. Figure 6 shows the outer & inner views of the prototype and the autoclave.

Before we execute the loading test, the strain sensor location should be decided. As a result of structural loading analysis, 130 points of sensor location could be determined. The static loading test was simulated by FE analysis to estimate strain on the sensor location, to compare with the loading test results.

Fig. 7: (a) Fiber dir. strain in composite skin at compressive loading (MPa),
 (b) deformed shape at vertical loading (y-dir., mm)

Fig. 8: Determined strain gage location

MODAL ANALYSIS

Modal analysis was performed to estimate the natural frequency of the prototype, using same FE model and same boundary condition as vertical loading test case. The calculated natural frequencies and the mode shapes of train prototype are presented in Fig. 8. The first bending mode was 2nd mode, 11.67 Hz, and the first twisting mode was 3rd mode, 14.39Hz. So, it can be confirmed that both modes showed natural frequencies above design limit, 10 Hz.

Fig. 9: (a) First bending mode shape(11.67 Hz), and (b) first twisting mode shape(14.39 Hz)

CONCLUSION

In this study, finite element analysis was conducted to simulate static loading test in order to design and confirm the structural safety of composite carbody structure of TTX. The result

showed the low stress level and Tsai-Wu index in composite structure and satisfied the design limit. The weight of the total carbody is about 7.19 ton, and the weight of composite structure is only 1.79 ton. For static loading test, structural analysis of train prototype model was conducted to estimate strain on the sensor location, to compare with the loading test results.

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